

Baltic Individual Crisis Preparedness Barometer

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Introduction

Russia's full-scale invasion of Ukraine and persistent hybrid tactics - including disinformation campaigns, cyberattacks, pressure on critical infrastructure, and military intimidation - have shattered assumptions of long-term stability in the Baltic Sea region. These aggressive actions have direct and indirect effects on the security environment in Lithuania, Latvia, and Estonia, underscoring the urgency of robust crisis preparedness at both societal and household levels.

At the same time, contemporary urban areas are increasingly exposed to a broad and interconnected spectrum of hazards, including climate change-driven extreme weather events, pandemics, technological failures, infrastructure disruptions, and hybrid security threats that interact in complex and often unpredictable ways.¹ As cities continue to grow and populations concentrate, a rising share of residents are exposed to these risks, frequently in environments where protective measures and preparedness capacities remain limited.²

Against this backdrop, these policy guidelines assess the level of crisis preparedness among residents of Vilnius, Riga, and Tallinn by examining urban readiness for emerging risks in the Baltic capitals. The analysis focuses on how prepared households are to prevent, withstand, and respond to a range of potential crises, including natural hazards, technological disruptions, and geopolitical threats. The guidelines examine how secure residents feel in their immediate neighborhoods, cities, and countries; what knowledge, resources, and practices households have in place to respond effectively to emergencies; and which demographic groups face heightened vulnerability.

¹ Gencer, Ebru, Regina Folorunsho, Megan Linkin, Xiaoming Wang, Claudia E. Natenzon, Shiraz Wajih, Nivedita Mani, Maricarmen Esquivel, Somayya Ali Ibrahim, Hori Tsuneki, Ricardo Castro, Mattia Federico Leone, Dilnoor Panjwani, Patricia Romero-Lankao, and William Solecki. "Disasters and Risk in Cities." In *Climate Change and Cities: Second Assessment Report of the Urban Climate Change Research Network*, edited by Cynthia Rosenzweig, William D. Solecki, Patricia Romero-Lankao, Shagun Mehrotra, Shobhakar Dhakal, and Somayya Ali Ibrahim, 61–98. New York: Cambridge University Press, 2018.; Zhang, Yueqian, Xinchun Li, and Quanlong Liu. "Advancing Urban Resilience: A Multi-Hazard Risk Perspective on Frontier Evolution, Research Hotspots, and Practical Exploration." *Urban Climate* 60 (2025): 102342. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.uclim.2025.102342>.

² United Nations Office for Disaster Risk Reduction (UNDRR), *Global Assessment Report on Disaster Risk Reduction 2025*. <https://www.undrr.org/gar/gar2025#download>. Accessed January 27, 2026.

The policy guidelines are based on a representative survey of 3,016 respondents conducted in Riga, Tallinn, and Vilnius in April-May 2025. The survey examines public perceptions of a broad spectrum of risks and evaluates household preparedness in relation to national preparedness recommendations. To complement the survey findings, 12 expert interviews were conducted between September and December 2025 with crisis preparedness specialists from municipal authorities, emergency services, national institutions, academia, and non-governmental organizations. These interviews provide insight into governance challenges affecting preparedness, including communication, coordination, and public engagement.

By combining population-level data with expert perspectives, the policy guidelines provide an evidence base for strengthening urban crisis preparedness and support targeted, actionable recommendations for national and municipal decision-makers in the Baltic capitals. While the guidelines are grounded in the specific security, institutional, and societal contexts of the Baltic cities, the findings and recommendations are also relevant to a broader set of countries facing similar challenges related to hybrid threats, urban vulnerability, and civilian preparedness. As such, policy insights may inform crisis-preparedness planning and resilience-building efforts beyond Northern Europe, particularly in states with comparable governance structures, urban environments, or exposure to various hazards.

Individual Preparedness and Risk Awareness in the Baltic Capitals

This section draws on both survey data and expert input to assess urban preparedness in the Baltic capitals. Combining population-level evidence with institutional perspectives makes it possible to understand how residents perceive risks, evaluate their own level of preparedness, and engage with public authorities within complex urban environments. The following sections summarize key findings on perceived security and threat levels and highlight governance and institutional factors that influence preparedness and resilience in Riga, Tallinn, and Vilnius.

Survey results show that, despite increased awareness of potential threats in recent years,³ residents’ overall sense of security remains relatively strong. Among respondents aged 18-74 in all three capitals, more than 90% report feeling secure in their immediate neighborhoods. A majority also consider their city and country to be safe places to live, although small differences exist between the capitals. By comparison, perceptions of the European Union as a secure place to live are lower across all three cities.

Perceptions of security vary across demographic groups. In Riga, younger respondents (aged 18–29) and those identifying as Latvian are more likely than the city average to view their neighborhood, city, country, and the EU as secure. Respondents identifying as Russian or other nationalities are less likely to perceive the EU as secure, and respondents identifying as Russian also express lower confidence in national security. In Tallinn, higher levels of perceived security are reported by younger respondents and those identifying as Estonian, while older respondents (aged 60–74) and those identifying as Russian or other nationalities report lower levels of perceived security at both national and EU levels. In Vilnius, respondents aged 30–39 are more likely to view the EU as secure, whereas respondents aged 60–74 report lower perceptions of security at city, national, and EU levels.

Overall, the findings indicate that while confidence in security remains high at the neighborhood, city, and national levels, perceptions of broader regional security are less positive. Differences by age and nationality point to the need for targeted preparedness policies, communication strategies, and engagement measures that address varying levels of risk perception and strengthen inclusive urban preparedness across the Baltic capitals.

Evaluation of threats Feeling secure: comparison	Average	Riga	Tallinn	Vilnius
Your immediate neighbourhood is a secure place to live in.	92%	90%	93%	92%
Your CITY is a secure place to live in	88%	82%	91%	91%
Your COUNTRY is a secure place to live in	86%	79%	90%	88%
The EU is a secure place to live in	76%	72%	77%	79%

Please select one response to what extent do you agree or disagree with each of the following statements.
Base: all respondents: Latvia (Riga), n=1004; Estonia (Tallinn), n=1008; Lithuania (Vilnius), n=1004.

Fig. 1. Perceived security across neighborhood, city, national, and EU levels.

³ Gioe, David V., Marina Miron, and Marc Ozawa. 2025. “Reassessing NATO’s Deterrence and Defence Posture in the Baltics: Rebalancing Strategic Priorities to Counter Russian Hybrid Aggression.” *Defense & Security Analysis* 41 (1): 145–65. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14751798.2024.2424935>.

In the current geopolitical and economic environment in Europe, perceptions of the most significant threats differ across the Baltic capitals, reflecting variations in public concern (Fig. 2). In Riga, respondents most frequently identify Latvia’s economic situation (58%), disruptions to critical supplies such as electricity and water (57%), a potential military attack against Latvia (56%), the spread of false or misleading information (54%), and the use of chemical, biological, or nuclear substances (49%) as key risks. In Tallinn, the most prominent concerns are the spread of false or misleading information (62%), the risk of a military attack against Estonia (52%), Estonia’s economic situation (50%), disruptions to digital services, including cyberattacks (46%), and disruptions to critical supplies (45%). In Vilnius, the risk of a military attack against Lithuania is the most frequently cited concern (67%). This is followed by the spread of false or misleading information (59%), disruptions to digital services (55%), the use of chemical, biological, or nuclear substances (55%), and disruptions to critical supplies (54%).

These variations underline the importance of tailoring preparedness and communication measures to city-specific risk perceptions while addressing common cross-cutting threats across the Baltic capitals.

Evaluation of threats Major threats: comparison	Average	Riga	Tallinn	Vilnius
Spread of false or misleading information	58%	54%	62%	59%
Military attack against COUNTRY (e.g. air raids)	58%	56%	52%	67%
Disrupted digital services (e.g. due to cyber-attacks)	48%	44%	46%	55%
Organised crime	43%	47%	33%	50%
Disrupted critical supplies (e.g. electricity, water)	52%	57%	45%	54%
COUNTRY’s economic situation	45%	58%	50%	28%
Terrorism	41%	42%	30%	50%
Use of chemical, biological or nuclear substances	45%	49%	30%	55%
Impact of climate change (e.g. more floods, storms)	35%	35%	27%	44%
Spread of infectious diseases	45%	47%	38%	49%
Threatening use of new technologies e.g. artificial intelligence)	32%	34%	25%	36%

Please rate each threat.
Base: all respondents: Latvia (Riga), n=1004; Estonia (Tallinn), n=1008; Lithuania (Vilnius), n=1004.

Fig. 2. Evaluation of major threats: comparative analysis.

Survey results also indicate clear demographic differences in how threats are perceived. Women and older respondents are more likely to identify a wider range of threats as major concerns across Riga, Tallinn, and Vilnius. In addition, respondents identifying with the local majority nationality tend to express higher levels of concern for certain risks than Russian-speaking respondents. These patterns indicate that age, gender, and national or cultural identity influence how threats are assessed in urban European contexts and should be taken into account in preparedness planning and risk communication.

The survey further highlights attitudes and self-assessed preparedness related to crisis response. A large majority of respondents - 81% in Vilnius and 76% in both Riga and Tallinn - state that it is important to regularly discuss disaster and emergency response with family members, friends, neighbours, or colleagues (Fig. 3). At the same time, perceptions of personal preparedness vary across cities. In Riga, 68% of respondents report having the necessary knowledge and skills to respond effectively in a disaster or emergency, compared to 60% in Tallinn and 44% in Vilnius. However, substantially fewer respondents across all three capitals report knowing where to go in the event of a rapid evacuation.

Despite a marked increase in perceived risk in recent years - linked to Russia's ongoing war against Ukraine and heightened security warnings across Europe - only a minority of respondents expect a major disaster or emergency to occur within the next ten years. This view is shared by 28% of respondents in Riga, 34% in Tallinn, and 26% in Vilnius. These findings point to a gap between rising external risk factors and public expectations, with implications for preparedness communication and engagement strategies.

Evaluation of threats Disaster/emergency: comparison	Average	Riga	Tallinn	
It is important to have regular discussions with family, friends, neighbours or colleagues about what to do in a disaster/emergency	78%	76%	76%	
I have the necessary knowledge and skills to respond effectively to a disaster/emergency	57%	68%	60%	
I know where to go in a disaster/emergency when I need to leave home urgently	40%	29%	44%	
I expect that a major disaster/emergency will happen in the next 10 years	29%	28%	34%	

Please select one response to what extent do you agree or disagree with each of the following statements.
Base: all respondents: Latvia (Riga), n=1004; Estonia (Tallinn), n=1008; Lithuania (Vilnius), n=1004.

Fig. 3. Disaster preparedness: awareness and perceived likelihood.

Across the Baltic capitals, respondents identify radio and mobile notifications as the most trusted channels for receiving information during crises, ranking well above television, online news portals, and social media platforms (Fig. 4). These preferences highlight the continued importance of direct and reliable communication tools in emergency situations.

Differences are evident across cities. In Tallinn, respondents report significantly higher trust in news portals than in television, with news portals trusted at approximately twice the level of television. In Vilnius, by contrast, television is regarded as a more trusted communication channel than in Riga or Tallinn, indicating variation in media consumption and trust across the capitals.

Trust in information channels also varies by nationality. In Riga, respondents identifying as Latvian report substantially higher trust in radio than Russian-speaking respondents (39% compared to 17%). In Tallinn, Russian-speaking respondents express markedly lower trust in television than respondents identifying as Estonian (8% compared to 36%). At the same time, Russian-speaking respondents in both Riga and Tallinn report higher levels of trust in mobile notifications than respondents identifying as Latvian or Estonian. In Riga, 31% of Russian-speaking respondents trust mobile notifications compared to 19% of Latvian respondents, while in Tallinn the respective figures are 42% and 31%.

These findings underline the need for diversified and targeted crisis communication strategies that account for differences in media trust across cities and population groups.

Evaluation of threats The most trusted channel: comparison	Average	Riga	Tallinn	Vilnius
Radio	30%	29%	28%	34%
Mobile notifications (SMS, apps)	27%	25%	35%	22%
TV	14%	12%	7%	23%
News portals	11%	12%	14%	6%
Social networks	5%	6%	4%	4%
Other	2%	2%	2%	3%
I don't know	11%	14%	9%	9%

Which information channel would you trust the most in an emergency?
 Base: all respondents: Latvia (Riga), n=1004; Estonia (Tallinn), n=1008; Lithuania (Vilnius), n=1004.

Fig. 4. Most trusted emergency communication channels.

Although radio is identified as the most trusted source of information during emergencies in all surveyed capitals - except Tallinn, where mobile notifications are ranked highest - survey results indicate limited household access to this medium. Fewer than one-third of respondents across Riga, Tallinn, and Vilnius report having a battery-powered AM/FM radio at home (Fig. 5), pointing to a potential gap between trusted communication channels and actual preparedness.

Clear differences emerge across age groups. In all three capitals, younger respondents (aged 18–29) are significantly less likely to own a battery-powered radio than older respondents. Only 12% of respondents in this age group in Riga, 10% in Tallinn, and 12% in Vilnius report having such a device. By comparison, ownership among respondents aged 60–74 is substantially higher, reaching 40% in Riga, 53% in Tallinn, and 43% in Vilnius.

These findings highlight the need to address generational disparities in access to trusted emergency communication tools and to consider age-specific measures when strengthening household-level preparedness.

Do you have a battery-powered AM FM radio at home?
 Base: all respondents: Latvia (Riga), n=1004; Estonia (Tallinn), n=1008; Lithuania (Vilnius), n=1004.

Fig. 5. Proportion of respondents with battery-powered AM/FM radios at home.

In recent years, both national governments and municipal authorities in the Baltic States have increased their focus on emergency shelters. However, survey results indicate substantial differences in public awareness of shelter locations across the capitals. Awareness is highest in Vilnius, where 51% of respondents report knowing the location of the nearest emergency shelter. In Tallinn, this share is significantly lower at 28%, while in Riga awareness is particularly limited, with only 14% of respondents able to identify the nearest shelter (Fig. 6).

These findings point to uneven levels of public awareness and highlight the need for improved communication, mapping, and public guidance on shelter availability, particularly in cities where awareness remains low.

Fig. 6. Awareness of the nearest emergency shelter.

Survey results also highlight limited household preparedness with regard to drinking water supplies. When asked how long their household water reserves would last - defined as three litres per household member - approximately one-third of respondents in each capital report having sufficient water for only 24 hours (Fig. 7). Given the critical importance of water access in urban settings, an additional concern is that around one-quarter of respondents report having no emergency water supplies at all.

These findings indicate a significant gap in basic household preparedness and underscore the need for clearer guidance, public awareness campaigns, and targeted measures to improve water storage practices in urban households.

Evaluation of threats Having drinking water supplies	Average	Riga	Tallinn	Vilnius
24 hrs	31%	31%	33%	30%
48 hrs	18%	17%	19%	17%
72 hrs	14%	14%	12%	16%
For about a week	6%	7%	7%	5%
More than a week	3%	2%	3%	4%
Prefer not to say	1%	2%	1%	1%
I don't have supplies	26%	27%	25%	27%

How long would drinking water supplies in your home last (3 Liters of water per household member)?
Base: all respondents: Latvia (Riga), n=1004; Estonia (Tallinn), n=1008; Lithuania (Vilnius), n=1004.

Fig. 7. Household drinking water supplies and duration.

Compared to rural households in the Baltic States - where small-scale food production often allows families to maintain reserves - urban households face greater vulnerability in the event of supply disruptions. Survey findings on household food supplies in Riga, Tallinn, and Vilnius shows that most respondents have at least some food provisions in place (Fig. 8). Nevertheless, a non-negligible share of respondents report having no food reserves at all: 7% in Riga, 5% in Tallinn, and 7% in Vilnius.

At the same time, approximately 44% of respondents in Riga, 45% in Tallinn, and 47% in Vilnius indicate that their food supplies would last for one week or longer. In contrast, 8% of respondents in each capital report having sufficient food for only 24 hours.

These results highlight both the relative resilience of a portion of urban households and the continued vulnerability of others, underscoring the need for targeted measures to strengthen basic food preparedness in urban environments.

Evaluation of threats Having food supplies	Average	Riga	Tallinn	Vilnius
24 hrs	8%	8%	8%	8%
48 hrs	14%	14%	15%	12%
72 hrs	25%	25%	25%	25%
For about a week	32%	30%	34%	31%
More than a week	14%	14%	11%	16%
Prefer not to say	2%	3%	1%	1%
I don't have supplies	6%	7%	5%	7%

How long would food supplies in your home last (for all household members)?
Base: all respondents: Latvia (Riga), n=1004; Estonia (Tallinn), n=1008; Lithuania (Vilnius), n=1004.

Fig. 8. Household food supplies and duration.

Survey responses regarding household first aid supplies and essential medications for all household members indicate that the majority of respondents across the three capitals report having at least some supplies available (Fig. 9). However, a notable minority report having no such supplies: 9% of respondents in Riga, 5% in Tallinn, and 9% in Vilnius.

In terms of duration, approximately 23% of respondents in Riga, 25% in Tallinn, and 23% in Vilnius report having sufficient first aid supplies and medications to last for one month or longer. At the same time, a smaller but significant share of respondents indicate very limited preparedness. In Riga and Vilnius, 12% report having supplies for less than three days, while in Tallinn this applies to 8% of respondents.

These findings point to uneven levels of medical preparedness across urban households and highlight the need for clear guidance on minimum first aid and medication reserves as part of household preparedness planning.

Having the first aid supplies and medications	Average	Riga	Tallinn	Vilnius
Less than 3 days	11%	12%	8%	12%
4-7 days	20%	16%	20%	23%
2 weeks	18%	15%	21%	17%
3-4 weeks	16%	16%	17%	14%
1-2 months	17%	15%	19%	16%
More than 3 months	7%	8%	6%	7%
Prefer not to say	5%	9%	4%	3%
I don't have stocks of first aid supplies and medications	8%	9%	5%	9%

How long would the first aid supplies and medications in your home (for all residents) last?
 Base: all respondents: Latvia (Riga), n=1004; Estonia (Tallinn), n=1008; Lithuania (Vilnius), n=1004.

Fig. 9. Household first aid supplies and medications.

In crisis situations, access to electronic payment systems may be disrupted, limiting the ability to purchase essential goods such as food and drinking water. In this context, the availability of physical cash remains an important component of household preparedness. Although this issue must be considered within the broader shift toward cashless transactions, experience from recent global crises demonstrates that cash continues to play a critical role during emergencies.

Survey results show that the majority of respondents in the Baltic capitals report having at least some cash set aside for essential purchases. However, a significant share of residents report having no cash reserves at all: 19% in Riga, 20% in Tallinn, and 13% in Vilnius (Fig. 10). In terms of duration, 48% of respondents in Riga, 47% in Tallinn, and 54% in Vilnius indicate that their cash reserves would be sufficient for one week or longer. By contrast, 10% in Riga, 11% in Tallinn, and 9% in Vilnius report having enough cash to cover essential needs for only 24 hours.

These findings highlight the continued relevance of cash in emergency preparedness and point to the need for clearer guidance on maintaining adequate cash reserves as part of household-level preparedness in urban settings.

Evaluation of threats Having enough cash reserves	Average	Riga	Tallinn	Vilnius
24 hrs	10%	10%	11%	9%
48 hrs	7%	5%	9%	6%
72 hrs	8%	8%	8%	8%
For about a week	19%	19%	20%	17%
More than a week	31%	28%	27%	37%
Prefer not to say	8%	10%	4%	9%
I don't have cash reserves	17%	19%	20%	13%

For how long would you have enough cash reserves to make essential purchases?
 Base: all respondents: Latvia (Riga), n=1004; Estonia (Tallinn), n=1008; Lithuania (Vilnius), n=1004.

Fig. 10. Availability and duration of household cash reserves.

Survey results indicate limited preparedness at workplaces and educational institutions in the Baltic capitals. On average, only one-fifth to one-sixth of respondents report that their place of employment or educational institution has reserves of drinking water, food, and essential medicines sufficient for 72 hours: 18% in Riga, 20% in Tallinn, and 15% in Vilnius (Fig. 11).

This finding is particularly relevant given that crises may occur without warning and during regular working hours, when many adults are at work and children and young people are in kindergartens and schools. Of additional concern is that approximately half of respondents across the three capitals report not knowing whether such reserves exist at their workplace or educational institution.

These results point to significant gaps in institutional preparedness and communication and underline the need for clearer standards, oversight, and information-sharing regarding emergency supplies in workplaces and educational settings.

Does your place of employment/educational institution have drinking water, food and medicine reserves for 72 hrs?
 Base: all respondents: Latvia (Riga), n=1004; Estonia (Tallinn), n=1008; Lithuania (Vilnius), n=1004.

Fig. 11. Workplace and educational institution emergency supplies.

Preparedness for crises that disrupt communication networks is a critical concern. Survey results indicate that most residents in the Baltic capitals - particularly in Riga and Tallinn - have not discussed contingency plans within their families and have not established an agreed-upon meeting point in the event of communication failure (Fig. 12). Only 6% of respondents in Riga and 9% in Tallinn report having a designated family meeting location. In Vilnius, the proportion is notably higher at 18%.

These findings highlight a significant gap in household-level contingency planning for communication failures and underscore the need for public awareness campaigns and guidance to encourage families to develop clear, practical plans for such scenarios.

Fig. 12. Agreed family meeting locations during communication disruption.

The survey initially asked respondents whether they felt they had the knowledge and skills necessary to respond effectively in a disaster or emergency (Fig. 3). In Riga and Tallinn, the majority of respondents - 68% and 60%, respectively - answered affirmatively. In Vilnius, considerably fewer respondents (44%) reported feeling adequately knowledgeable and skilled.

As the survey progressed, more detailed questions were posed, including knowledge of the location of the nearest emergency shelter and the status of household food and water reserves. Responses to these specific questions revealed notable discrepancies between respondents' initial self-assessments and their actual level of preparedness, indicating gaps between perceived and actual readiness.

Overall, the assessment of household preparedness for crisis situations highlights significant shortfalls (Fig. 13). Across all respondents, only 20% in Tallinn and Vilnius reported feeling adequately prepared for emergencies, while in Riga the proportion was even lower at 16%. Preparedness levels were particularly low among female respondents, pointing to demographic differences that should be considered when designing targeted preparedness initiatives and communication strategies.

Taking into account the above, do you feel adequately prepared for crisis/emergency situations?
Base: all respondents: Latvia (Riga), n=1004; Estonia (Tallinn), n=1008; Lithuania (Vilnius), n=1004.

Fig. 13. Overall household preparedness for crises and emergencies.

Analysis of the main barriers preventing respondents from adequately preparing for crises or emergencies identifies three primary obstacles across all surveyed cities: the psychological difficulty of considering such scenarios, a perceived lack of need or immediate threat, and insufficient information (Fig. 14). In Vilnius, more than half of respondents reported that the main barrier is the psychological challenge of thinking about crises. In Riga and Tallinn, this concern was also noted, though less pronounced.

Differences by age group are particularly significant. Younger respondents (18–29) are much more likely than older respondents (60–74) to cite lack of time as a barrier to preparedness. Among the younger group, 22% in Riga, 35% in Tallinn, and 35% in Vilnius reported time constraints as a limiting factor, compared with only 5% in Riga, 6% in Tallinn, and 8% in Vilnius of respondents aged 60–74.

These findings have important implications for municipal crisis-preparedness strategies in the Baltic capitals. They highlight the need for targeted approaches to engage younger residents, who - due to the pace, demands, and competing priorities of daily life - may find it especially challenging to prioritize or even consider preparedness measures. Tailored outreach, education, and practical guidance could help address these barriers and strengthen overall urban resilience.

Obstacles to prepare for crisis/emergency situations	Average	Riga	Tallinn	Vilnius
Psychologically difficult to think about	43%	35%	37%	58%
Don't feel the need/ lack of threat	33%	41%	34%	25%
Lack of information	29%	37%	26%	23%
Lack of financial resources	22%	24%	25%	18%
Lack of time	18%	13%	21%	20%
Someone else should take care of it	4%	5%	3%	3%
Other	4%	2%	7%	3%
Prefer not to say	2%	3%	2%	2%

What hinders you from adequately preparing for crisis/emergency situations?
 Base: all respondents: Latvia (Riga), n=740; Estonia (Tallinn), n=764; Lithuania (Vilnius), n=744.

Fig. 14. Key obstacles to household crisis and emergency preparedness.

Building on the analysis of barriers to preparedness, the survey also examined the types of support and resources that residents believe would help them better prepare for disasters and emergencies (Fig. 15).

In Riga, 58% of respondents reported that having more information on what to do during a disaster or emergency would improve their preparedness. In Tallinn, the primary need, cited by 55% of respondents, is neighborhood-level awareness-raising activities to help residents understand where to seek assistance during a crisis. In Vilnius, the leading need, noted by a slightly higher share of respondents, is greater investment in infrastructure, including sirens and emergency shelters, with 45% of respondents indicating that these measures would improve preparedness.

Ethnicity also plays a role in perceived support needs, particularly in Riga and Tallinn, where Russian-speaking populations are substantial. In Latvia, 45% of Russian-speaking respondents indicated that financial support - such as assistance to stock essential supplies - would improve preparedness, compared with 31% of ethnic Latvians. In Estonia, a similar pattern emerged: 27% of ethnic Estonians reported a need for financial support, while 54% of Russian speakers in Tallinn identified government assistance as important.

Evaluation of threats Needs from the authorities/government	Average	Riga	Tallinn	Vilnius
More detailed information about what I should do in the event of a disaster emergency (e.g. leaflets, media)	46%	58%	39%	42%
Awareness-raising activities in my neighbourhood so I know where to turn in case of a disaster/emergency	50%	50%	55%	44%
Increased investment in infrastructure (e.g. sirens, shelters)	42%	37%	44%	45%
Financial support (e.g. to stock up my supplies)	34%	37%	33%	34%
The existing information is sufficient for me	8%	7%	9%	10%
Additional needs (not listed above)	3%	2%	3%	4%

What do you need from the authorities/ government to become better prepared for potential disaster or emergency?
 Base: all respondents: Latvia (Riga), n=1004; Estonia (Tallinn), n=1008; Lithuania (Vilnius), n=1004.

Fig. 15. Perceived needs from authorities to improve disaster preparedness.

Gender differences are also evident. Across all three capitals, women are more likely than men to report a need for detailed guidance on what to do during a disaster or emergency, as well as for neighborhood-level awareness activities to identify where to turn for help.

These findings highlight the importance of targeted, inclusive strategies to strengthen preparedness, taking into account differences by ethnicity, gender, and local context.

Examples of Best Practice

Following the survey analysis of household and institutional preparedness in the Baltic capitals, in-depth interviews with crisis-preparedness experts provide complementary insights into effective strategies, innovative approaches, and lessons learned from real-world practice. These expert perspectives highlight concrete mechanisms, campaigns, and operational structures that have successfully strengthened urban and national resilience, offering examples that can inform policy, planning, and public engagement across the region. Drawing on experiences from Lithuania, Latvia, and Estonia, the following section presents illustrative best practices demonstrating how coordinated institutions, public awareness initiatives, infrastructure improvements, and practical household guidance can collectively enhance readiness for a wide range of crises.

Semi-structured interviews were conducted between September and December 2025 with twelve crisis-preparedness specialists from municipal administrations, emergency and rescue services, national crisis-preparedness bodies, academia, and non-governmental organizations. The interviews focused on assessments of public preparedness at both municipal and national levels, institutional approaches to designing and implementing preparedness activities, and governance conditions that facilitate or constrain civil preparedness. Experts were also asked to reflect on gaps between citizens' perceived security and their actual household-level readiness, the measures institutions use to address these gaps, challenges related to building and maintaining public trust, and strategies for ensuring credible crisis communication and raising awareness of household preparedness.

Lithuania

Interviews and analysis of Lithuania's crisis preparedness reveal several **key lessons for effective urban and national resilience**. Experts emphasize **coordination between national institutions and local actors** as a cornerstone of readiness, enabling rapid information flow, joint decision-making, and efficient response during crises. Multi-agency collaboration, public awareness campaigns, and infrastructure mapping are consistently cited as essential mechanisms for strengthening resilience and ensuring continuity of essential services. The Emergency Response Centre (ERC) plays a central operational role, providing 24/7 response coordination, assessing incoming emergency calls, dispatching services, and guiding citizens until help arrives. Its integration with the National Crisis Management Centre ensures that real-time operational data informs national-level strategic decision-making, demonstrating the value of linking operational and strategic levels to enhance system effectiveness and crisis anticipation.

Experts stressed that **public awareness alone is insufficient to guarantee household preparedness**. While campaigns provide knowledge and guidance, citizens often fail to translate this into concrete action, such as assembling emergency supplies, identifying shelter locations, or establishing family contingency plans. Public education campaigns are most effective when paired with actionable steps, practical drills, or neighborhood-level exercises. This underscores the necessity of initiatives that bridge the gap between knowledge and action, emphasizing individual responsibility alongside structured communication.

The national campaign, “**We are a team. We have a plan**” (“**Esame komanda. Turime planą**”), which used basketball as a central theme to engage the public, demonstrates best practice in large-scale public engagement. Launched in 2023,⁴ the campaign delivered unified messaging through television, radio, social media, and print, reaching two million residents within two months. By linking the principles of teamwork and planning from basketball to household and community-level preparedness, it successfully promoted active participation in readiness measures, increased engagement with emergency kit guidance, and helped reduce misinformation during local incidents. These efforts illustrate the critical role of structured, consistent communication and creative, culturally resonant messaging in shaping citizens’ perceptions of their responsibilities during crises.

Lithuania conducted a **nationwide review and formalization of more than 6,400 public shelters**, providing potential protection for approximately 1.5 million people, or around 54% of the population. In parallel, **updated legal requirements for shelters in newly constructed buildings** were introduced to address contemporary threats, including drones and missile attacks, ensuring faster access, improved safety standards, and greater relevance to current security risks. Accessible, well-mapped, and clearly communicated shelter infrastructure directly improves citizen readiness and reduces panic during emergencies. Geographic disparities remain, with populations near high-risk areas showing higher awareness, while vulnerable groups, including people with disabilities, require tailored interventions to ensure equitable preparedness.

Participation in **exercises and practical training** is consistently highlighted as a key factor in increasing readiness. Hands-on engagement, including drills, simulations, and tabletop exercises, substantially improves risk awareness, knowledge retention, and the likelihood of appropriate response during crises. A generational gap in preparedness was also noted, with younger residents less likely to take practical measures due to limited experience with past crises, emphasizing the importance of age-targeted educational initiatives.

Finally, experts stress **small, actionable preparedness measures** that households can implement immediately, such as creating a family emergency plan and practicing it regularly. The gap between perceived and actual readiness is notable, as individuals without prior crisis experience often overestimate their preparedness. The overarching lesson is that resilience depends on **multi-agency coordination, integration of civil and military preparedness, strategic infrastructure investment**, continuous monitoring, and education that combines awareness with practical action, ensuring that citizens are genuinely prepared for crises.

⁴ “Lithuania Launches Campaign to Prep Society for War, Crises.” LRT.lt, January 10, 2023. https://www.lrt.lt/en/news-in-english/19/1863164/lithuania-launches-campaign-to-prep-society-for-war-crises?srsId=AfmBOoqPs5LI9WC_jJU4h2zsiTsZGcPQMcb1FRsZ23WcN-a2lk2Kjo1z (accessed February 5, 2026).

⁵ “Lithuanian Municipalities to Spend €12 m on Bomb Shelters.” BNS / LRT.lt, March 20, 2025. <https://www.lrt.lt/en/news-in-english/19/2517448/lithuanian-municipalities-to-spend-eur12m-on-bomb-shelters> (accessed February 5, 2026).

Latvia

Interviews and analysis of Latvia's crisis preparedness highlight several key lessons for strengthening urban and national resilience. **A clear division of responsibilities, combined with stronger national coordination**, has emerged as a central factor in improving readiness, helping to reduce fragmentation between state institutions and municipalities and enabling more coherent responses during complex crises. The establishment of a centralized crisis management structure - most notably the creation of the National Crisis Management Center in 2025 - together with improved data sharing and situational awareness, demonstrates the importance of integrating strategic decision-making with operational capacities across sectors.

Experts consistently emphasize that **municipalities remain pivotal to effective crisis response**, as they are responsible for local planning, public communication, evacuation, and community-level implementation. Preparedness is strongest where municipalities actively invest in civil protection planning, maintain regular communication with residents, and cooperate closely with emergency services, NGOs, and critical infrastructure operators. Community drills, seminars, and workshops are particularly effective, serving both to educate residents and to identify gaps in household preparedness while fostering informal neighborhood networks that can function independently during disruptions.

Public awareness initiatives, including guidance on 72-hour self-sufficiency and civil protection responsibilities, have contributed to a general culture of readiness. However, experts underline that **urban residents - especially in Riga - often overestimate their preparedness and remain highly reliant on continuous public services**. This reliance creates a gap between perceived safety and actual readiness, underscoring the need to move beyond information provision toward practical engagement. **Awareness campaigns are most effective when paired with hands-on activities** such as evacuation drills, first aid training, and scenario-based exercises that translate knowledge into action.

Municipal-level civil protection seminars should be expanded and systematically integrated into urban preparedness strategies, building on the positive experience in Riga, where regular seminars have strengthened residents' understanding of practical emergency measures.⁶

⁶ In Riga, 15 municipal civil protection seminars were held in 2024–2025, organized by the Riga District Residents' Centre (RAIC) in cooperation with the Civil Protection and Operational Information Department. The seminars focused on the "Resistance Handbook" and practical household-level preparedness measures, including sheltering options, personal responsibilities during crises, municipal support, 72-hour survival kits, communication methods, and psychological resilience. See: Rīgas pašvaldība. "Pēdējais civilās aizsardzības seminārs šogad notiks 26. novembrī Latgales apkaimē." Riga.lv, 2025. https://www.riga.lv/lv/jaunums/-pedejais-civilas-aizsardzibas-seminars-sogad-notiks-26-novembri-latgales-apkaime?utm_source=https%3A%2F%2Fwww.google.com%2F (accessed February 5, 2026).

Crisis communication itself is identified as a critical capability. Effective approaches balance transparency with psychological sensitivity, delivering guidance in gradual, manageable steps rather than through alarmist messaging. Continuous background communication helps build baseline awareness, enabling authorities to issue concise and actionable instructions when incidents occur. Open and targeted communication is seen as essential for countering misinformation, sustaining public trust, and reinforcing individual responsibility.

Practical exercises such as the “**Pilskalns 2025**” civil-military drill⁷ and annual **Namejs exercises**⁸ are highlighted as valuable examples, **strengthening civil-military cooperation, inter-agency coordination, and local readiness**. These initiatives provide citizens and municipalities with direct experience in responding to emergencies, fostering practical skills, situational awareness, and confidence in crisis response. These findings align with the LaSER report,⁹ which emphasizes that citizen participation in civil protection training significantly strengthens individual skills and preparedness for real crisis situations.

Interviews underline that **resilience in Latvia depends on shared responsibility across state institutions, municipalities, communities, and individuals**. Civil-military cooperation, regular exercises, and the integration of crisis planning into everyday governance strengthen preparedness at all levels. The overarching lesson is that urban resilience cannot rely on formal plans alone; it requires practical skills, strong community ties, locally adapted engagement, and sustained efforts to encourage citizens to take ownership of their own preparedness - particularly in large and socially diverse cities such as Riga.

Expanding initiatives such as “My Latvia. My Responsibility” (“Mana Latvija. Mana Atbildība”) into regular, locally anchored activities - through workplaces, schools, and community networks - would help translate abstract responsibility into concrete individual actions, strengthen everyday readiness for civil crises, and reinforce societal resilience as a foundation for national defense.

⁷ Ogre Municipality. “Ogres novadā notikušas civilmilitārās mācības ‘Pilskalns 2025’” Ogresnovads.lv, 2025. https://www.ogresnovads.lv/lv/jaunums/ogres-novada-notikumas-civilmilitaras-macibas-pilskalns-2025?utm_source=https%3A%2F%2Fwww.google.com%2F (accessed February 5, 2026).; Balods, Mārcis, and Marta Kepe. “Lessons from Latvia’s Efforts to Keep Essential Services Running During a Crisis.” RAND Corporation, August 18, 2025. <https://www.rand.org/pubs/commentary/2025/08/lessons-from-latvias-efforts-to-keep-essential-services.html> (accessed February 5, 2026).

⁸ Riga City Council. “Comprehensive National Defence Exercise Namejs 2025 Already Underway in Riga.” Riga.lv, 2025. <https://www.riga.lv/en/article/comprehensive-national-defence-exercise-namejs-2025-already-underway-riga> (accessed February 5, 2026).

⁹ Kits, Roberts, and Artis Vilks. No sirēnas līdz patvertnei? Civiltā aizsardzība Rīgā. Rīga: LaSER Latvijas Stratēģijas un Ekonomikas Risinājumu Institūts, December 18, 2025. <https://domnicalaser.lv/no-sirenas-lidz-patvertnei-civila-aizsardziba-riga/>

¹⁰ “Patriotic Motto Trademarked by Latvian National Guard.” LSM.lv, November 5, 2024. <https://eng.lsm.lv/article/society/defense/05.11.2024-patriotic-motto-trademarked-by-latvian-nationalguard.a575248/> (accessed February 6, 2026).

Estonia

Estonia's experience demonstrates that strong legal frameworks and advanced technological systems must be complemented by sustained, hands-on public engagement to translate preparedness into effective action. While national coordination and clear institutional roles are well established, policy efforts should further focus on ensuring that municipal capacities are sufficiently resourced and consistent across regions, particularly for smaller or resource-limited local governments responsible for frontline implementation.

Municipal-level preparedness should prioritize practical, experiential training over passive information dissemination. Interviews consistently show that hands-on activities - such as evacuation drills, shelter orientation, cooking without electricity, and community-based simulations- are far more effective than brochures or lectures in building real preparedness. These activities should be systematically integrated into municipal crisis plans, with special attention to apartment-heavy urban areas where self-organization and informal cooperation are weaker.

Crisis communication strategies should be adaptive, multilingual, and delivered in small, manageable steps. Estonia's provision of crisis guidance in Estonian, Russian, and English represents a noteworthy example, but experts emphasize that information overload reduces effectiveness. Policies should therefore emphasize phased communication, clear behavioral guidance, and repeated reinforcement, while actively addressing common misconceptions about evacuation options and crisis mobility.

Public responsiveness can be amplified by leveraging perceived risk and timely communication. The February 2025 synchronization of the Baltic electricity grid with the European power system demonstrated that even a single, well-timed social media post prompted immediate citizen action, highlighting the potential of rapid, credible information to motivate preparedness behaviors. Authorities should therefore use targeted alerts and real-time updates strategically to drive proactive household and community-level preparedness.

Practical exercises and education should continue to serve as a cornerstone of long-term resilience building. The integration of civil protection into school curricula is a strong foundation and should be reinforced through regular practical exercises and links between schools, families, and municipal preparedness activities. Children's role as multipliers of preparedness within households should be explicitly recognized and supported. Neighborhood-level outreach activities should also be systematically implemented to engage residents directly and build practical skills, particularly in areas with limited municipal capacity.

Technology and early warning systems require stronger integration with public behavior and municipal practice. While digital tools, sirens, and alert systems are operational, interviews reveal gaps in public understanding and response. Regular testing, public feedback loops, and training for both officials and citizens are essential to ensure that technological systems lead to timely and appropriate action during real emergencies.

Household self-sufficiency - particularly regarding water storage and shelter access - should be strengthened through realistic, space-sensitive guidance. Given structural constraints in urban housing, policies should promote feasible solutions for small apartments, expand access to public and shared shelters, and integrate water and shelter planning into building regulations and neighborhood-level preparedness efforts.

¹¹ Estonian Rescue Board. Ole Valmis – Emergency Preparedness Information. <https://www.olevalmis.ee/en> (accessed February 7, 2026).

Recommendations

In the Baltic capitals, survey results reveal notable gender, demographic, and city-level differences in both perceived threats and household preparedness. **Women consistently report higher perceived risks than men, particularly regarding military threats, misinformation, and disruptions to digital services, while men generally express greater confidence in their overall preparedness**¹². Gender differences are less pronounced for specific knowledge, such as the location of sirens or emergency shelters. Across cities, Vilnius respondents tend to report slightly higher preparedness levels compared to Riga and Tallinn, yet all three capitals exhibit gaps between perceived readiness and actual capabilities.

Targeted analysis further indicates that awareness of specific threats does not reliably translate into practical preparedness. **Higher concern about risks such as military attacks, cyber disruptions, or supply shortages is generally not associated with logically related actions, including storing water, maintaining cash reserves, or knowing emergency meeting points**¹³. In some instances, greater perceived threat was even linked to slightly lower preparedness, highlighting that risk awareness alone is insufficient to drive protective behavior.

Additionally, differences in perceived security across age groups, nationalities, and linguistic communities suggest that broader contextual factors influence preparedness. **Confidence in neighborhood, city, and national security remains relatively high, whereas perceptions of regional or EU-level security are lower, particularly among older residents and Russian-speaking populations.**

Taken together, these findings underscore the need for policy measures that combine practical, behavior-focused guidance with inclusive outreach. **Interventions should address demographic disparities, city-specific vulnerabilities, and behavioral gaps, emphasizing education, training, and engagement strategies that enable households and communities to translate awareness into effective preparedness**¹⁴.

City-specific variations in perceived threats highlight the importance of tailoring communication and preparedness efforts to local contexts. In Riga, residents are most concerned with economic stability, disruptions to critical supplies, and military risks, while in Tallinn, misinformation, cyberattacks, and military threats dominate public concern. In Vilnius, the risk of a military attack is the foremost concern, alongside digital service disruptions and chemical, biological, or nuclear threats. These differences point to the need for **preparedness campaigns that address both city-specific risks and common cross-cutting threats**, including misinformation, supply disruptions, and infrastructure vulnerabilities.

¹² Birka, Ieva and Guna Gavrilko. (forthcoming). Gender and Security in the Baltic Sea Region: A comparative study of northern and central European cities. In Biskupski-Mujanovic, S., Kitchen, V., and Narozhna, T. (eds): Gender and National Security.

¹³ Birka, Ieva and Didzis Kļaviņš. (forthcoming). Individual Threat Perception and Preparedness in Helsinki, Riga and German Cities. Submitted to Central European Journal of International and Security Studies.

¹⁴ Kļaviņš, Didzis and Ieva Birka. (forthcoming). Feeling Safe but Not Ready: Disaster Risk Perception, Preparedness Gaps, and Urban resilience in Baltic Capitals. Submitted to Progress in Disaster Science.

The gap between perceived and actual preparedness further highlights the importance of practical skill-building and household guidance. While a majority of respondents report discussing disaster response with family and community members, fewer can accurately identify evacuation routes or the location of emergency shelters. **Policies should promote regular household drills, guidance on evacuation procedures, and development of contingency plans**, including agreed meeting points and communication strategies for scenarios where networks fail. Special attention should be paid to younger residents, who are less likely to prioritize preparedness due to time constraints or psychological barriers.

Differences in media trust and access to emergency communication tools point to the need for diversified communication strategies. Residents identify radio and mobile notifications as the most trusted sources of information during crises, yet fewer than one-third of households possess battery-powered radios, and younger age groups are particularly under-equipped. **Policymakers should encourage acquisition of reliable communication devices, develop alternative channels to reach digitally native populations, and ensure messaging is tailored to trust differences across ethnic and linguistic groups.**

Crisis communication strategies should leverage **perceived risk and timely updates** to prompt immediate household action. Evidence shows that well-timed alerts, social media notifications, and local advisories can significantly increase proactive preparedness behaviors. Authorities should integrate these tools into a broader, adaptive communication framework, ensuring that messages are **clear, actionable, and culturally sensitive**, while reinforcing guidance delivered through hands-on exercises.

Household preparedness in essential resources shows notable gaps. Drinking water supplies are limited, with a third of respondents reporting only 24 hours of reserves and approximately one-quarter having no emergency water at all. Food supplies also reveal vulnerabilities, with a small but significant share of households having no reserves, and many only able to sustain themselves for 24 hours. First aid kits and medications are unevenly available, with 5–9% of households lacking essential medical supplies. Physical cash, which remains vital when electronic systems fail, is also inadequately maintained by a notable portion of households. **These findings highlight the need for clear guidance and support to help households build minimum standards for emergency resources**, emphasizing practical and scalable measures suitable for urban living.

Household self-sufficiency must be further strengthened, with particular emphasis on **water storage, shelter access, and small-space solutions**. Given structural constraints in urban apartments, policies should provide guidance on feasible water and food reserves, practical use of shared or public shelters, and maintaining essential items within limited living spaces. Support mechanisms, including municipal distribution points or subsidies for emergency supplies, should target households unable to maintain adequate reserves independently.

Institutional preparedness also requires urgent attention. Workplaces, schools, and other educational institutions frequently lack, or are perceived to lack, sufficient reserves of water, food, and medications for at least 72 hours, and many staff and students are unaware of available provisions. **Authorities should establish standardized emergency supply protocols, oversight mechanisms, and clear communication channels** to ensure institutional readiness, recognizing that crises often occur during working or school hours.

reserves have been established, organizations should actively inform and educate all personnel and occupants about their availability and proper use, ensuring an effective response during emergencies.

Generational and demographic disparities indicate that policies must be inclusive and context specific. Younger residents often cite time constraints as a barrier to preparedness, while older populations may face physical or informational challenges. Women are more likely to report a need for detailed guidance and neighborhood-level awareness activities. Ethnic minority groups, particularly Russian-speaking populations in Riga and Tallinn, identify financial or material support as critical for building household preparedness. **Municipal strategies should integrate targeted outreach, practical guidance, and support mechanisms that address the specific needs of each demographic group.**

Finally, there is a clear demand from residents for enhanced infrastructure and localized preparedness measures. Investment in emergency shelters, sirens, and community awareness programs can increase confidence and practical readiness. **Authorities should prioritize neighborhood-level engagement, including drills, educational initiatives, and accessible guidance materials,** while providing financial or logistical support for households that face obstacles in maintaining sufficient emergency supplies. By combining household, institutional, and community-focused measures, and tailoring interventions to local contexts and demographic needs, **policymakers can significantly enhance the resilience of urban populations in Riga, Tallinn, and Vilnius, ensuring citizens are better prepared to respond effectively to crises and emergencies.**

Practical exercises and experiential learning should be systematically expanded across municipalities. Scenario-based drills, evacuation exercises, shelter orientation, first aid workshops, and community simulations have been shown to strengthen knowledge retention, build confidence, and translate awareness into tangible preparedness. Policies should ensure that these activities are regular, locally anchored, and inclusive, particularly in neighborhoods with low social cohesion or high-density apartment complexes where self-organization is more difficult.

Education should continue to serve as a cornerstone for long-term resilience. Integrating civil protection into school and kindergarten curricula, reinforced through practical exercises and family-linked activities, allows children to act as multipliers of preparedness, influencing household behaviors and fostering a culture of readiness from an early age. Municipal authorities should coordinate with educational institutions to ensure continuity and alignment of preparedness initiatives with local crisis plans.

Municipal preparedness must integrate **community networks and social cohesion initiatives** to strengthen local resilience. Authorities should encourage neighborhood-level leadership, volunteer engagement, and active civic groups to facilitate practical exercises, disseminate guidance, and support residents during crises. Strengthening local networks is particularly critical in socially fragmented or linguistically diverse areas, where traditional outreach methods may be less effective.

For the next three years, progress in strengthening public awareness and readiness will be systematically monitored through the *Baltic Individual Crisis Preparedness Barometer*,

supported by the University of Latvia Large Impact Development Program, with a specific focus on eight metropolitan centers of the Baltic Sea region: Helsinki, Tallinn, Riga, Vilnius, Warsaw, the German cities of Berlin/Munich/Hamburg, Copenhagen, and Stockholm.

